

A Speech Act Analysis in the Chinese Cinderella Novel

Mia Purwati

(Department of English Literature, Gunadarma University, Indonesia)

ABSTRACT: *The most significant thing in speech act is the message that the speaker wants to deliver, it is not only words but also perform an action. The aims of this research are to analyze the speech acts and classify the illocutionary acts used in the Chinese Cinderella novel. This research used a descriptive qualitative as the method of the research. The result of the research shows that: (1) there are 137 utterances are considered as speech acts, and (2) there are 99 utterances of illocutionary acts found in this novel, which is the most dominant is assertive consist 28 utterances.*

KEYWORDS: *speech act, locutionary, illocutionary, perlocutionary.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Speech act is the study of intended meaning of spoken and written utterances. In addition, the most important things in speech acts is the message of the speaker's intention, so the listener understands the message from the speaker. Speech act is divided into three parts; a locutionary act, illocutionary act, and perlocutionary act. Speech act is the utterance which the speaker says, or the speaker performs in every speech.

The importance of studying speech act is to make comprehend what messages are found in every utterance. Usually, speech acts can be found in conversation. The conversation in the novel can be an excellent example of speech acts because it represents the complicated case of speech acts in order to find out what the main character does by saying something. The one of important that mostly occurred in the novel is the dialogue among the characters. In this research, the researcher wanted to analyze speech acts that are used in the novel. The researcher choosed Chinese Cinderella novel as the source of data because the novel is one of the best selling author. The novel was published on May 6th 2009 by Laurel Leaf. This novel is the true story of an unwanted daughter. Surprisingly, the unwanted daughter is the author herself. Therefore, the novel got the best selling author because the author inspired a lot of people and readers.

1.1 Problem Formulation

The questions that are related to the research were formulated as follow:

1. What are the speech acts used in Chinese Cinderella novel?
2. What are the classifications of illocutionary act used in Chinese Cinderella novel?

1.2 Previous Research

The researcher found one previous research as the reference for this research:

1. **Zulfa Tutuarima, Nuraeningsih, and Rusiana (2018) Muria Kudus University**

The title of their research is An Analysis of Speech Act Used in London Has Fallen Movie. The aim of their research are: (a) to find out the kinds of speech act used in London Has Fallen Movie, and (b) to find out the way of speech act and the classifications of illocutionary act used in London Has Fallen Movie. This research uses descriptive qualitative research. The result of the research shows that: (a) there are 76 utterances

of speech act used in London Has Fallen Movie which is the most dominant is illocutionary act consist of 37 utterances. (b) there are 99 utterances of the classifications of the illocutionary act, and the most dominant categories are directive with 32 utterances and expressive with 23 utterances.

1.3 Purpose of the Research

Referring to the problem of the research, the purposes of this research are:

1. To analyze the speech acts used in Chinese Cinderella novel.
2. To classify the illocutionary acts used in Chinese Cinderella novel.

Language is one of the essential things in human life. It is used to communicate with other people in their daily life, either spoken or written. It takes significant things because they can convey the intent and message. As the role of a language in general is to express the idea, feeling, and thought. Nowadays, using language for communication is necessary. The best result of communication itself is when the speaker and listener understand what they are talking about. The communicative act or called as the utterances of the speaker commonly represent verbal communication. It means that people do not only produce an utterance which is focused on grammatical structure and every word but also the way they perform the utterance.

Speech act is the study of intended meaning of spoken and written utterances. In addition, the most important things in speech acts is the message of the speaker's intention, so the listener understands the message from the speaker. Speech act is divided into three parts; a locutionary act, illocutionary act, and perlocutionary act. Speech act is the utterance which the speaker says, or the speaker performs in every speech.

The importance of studying speech act is to make comprehend what messages are found in every utterance. Usually, speech acts can be found in conversation. The conversation in the novel can be an excellent example of speech acts because it represents the complicated case of speech acts in order to find out what the main character does by saying something. The one of important that mostly occurred in the novel is the dialogue among the characters. In this research, the researcher wanted to analyze speech acts that are used in the novel. The researcher choosed Chinese Cinderella novel as the source of data because the novel is one of the best selling author. The novel was published on May 6th 2009 by Laurel Leaf. This novel is the true story of an unwanted daughter. Surprisingly, the unwanted daughter is the author herself. Therefore, the novel got the best selling author because the author inspired a lot of people and readers.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Pragmatics is concerned with the study of meanings as communicated by a speaker (or writer) and interpreted by a listener (or reader). It means that more to do with the analysis of what people mean by their utterances that what the words or phrases it those utterances might mean by themselves. Yule (1996) stated that speech act is a concern with the speaker's communicative intention in producing an utterance, and it is defined by the purpose for which the speakers use the language, for example, to make a request, to apologize, and to report stated. It means that the speech act is always used in daily life when speaker say something and listener knows the purpose of speaker's says in the communication so it will make the best result in the communication.

According to Austin (1969), there are two categories of utterance, namely constative utterances and performative utterances. Constative utterances is to those utterances which are used to describe or constate something, and those which thus are true or false. While, performative utterances is to those utterances not only perform a speech act beyond the assertion but also at the same time describe the speech act. In addition, Austin divided three parts of speech acts that are: (1) locutionary act, (2) illocutionary act, and (3) perlocutionary act.

(1) Locutionary Act

Locutionary acts are the act that is performed in order to communicate, the act of actual uttering (the particular sense and reference of an utterance) the study is the domain of field like phonetic, phonology, and linguistic semantics. Alternatively, in other words, a locutionary act is the basic act of utterance or producing a meaningful linguistic expression.

(2) Illocutionary Act

Illocutionary act is an act performed in saying something, making statement or promise, thanking, asking a question, etc. Alternatively, an illocutionary act is performed via the communicative force of an utterance such as making a statement, offer, explanation, or for some other communicative purpose.

(3) Perlocutionary Act

A perlocutionary act is an act performed by saying something in a particular context. It represents the change achieved each time, in a particular context. These acts are the by-products of acts of communication; acts performed using saying something, moving someone to anger, consoling someone in his distress, etc. It means to create an utterance with a function without intending it to affect.

Searle (1975) argued that the speech act is defined as an action changing the universe of discourse when a speaker utters it, and a recipient grasps it. It may be oral as well as written, or even expressed via some other communication from such as sign language. Searle divided five categories of illocutionary acts, they are:

1. Assertive
The purpose is to convey information about some states of affairs of the world from the speaker to the hearer, such as boast, assert, claim, characterize, state, diagnose, class, complain, and conclude.
2. Directives
Where the speaker requests the hearer to carry out some action or to bring about some states of affair such as order, command, insist, suggest, request, ask, beg, plead, pray, entreat, permit, and advise.
3. Commissive
The purpose is to show that the speaker undertakes to do something by expressing an intention such as promise, pledge, threaten, or any other words that match the criteria of commissive.
4. Expressive
The purpose is where speaker brings about some state of affairs by the more performance of the speech act or reveal the speaker's state of mind about a situation such as apologies, welcome, thanks, congratulate, console, or other words that match with expressive.
5. Declaratives
The purpose is where the speakers bring about some state of affairs by the more performance of the speech act or aim to create a change such as resign, appoint, declare, name, call, define, nominate, etc.

III. RESEARCH METHOD

3.1 Research Design

Research design is the set of steps that must be done by a researcher in analyzing data the research. According to Creswell (2009), "Research designs are plans and the procedures for research that span the decision from a broad assumption to detail method of data collection and analysis" (Creswell, 2009, p. 3). The method that the researcher used in this research was qualitative method. "Qualitative research is characterized by its purpose, that is related to understanding the social life aspects, and its methods generally produce words as data for analysis, rather than numbers" (Patton, 2002, p. 2). The data of this study were utterances found in Chinese Cinderella novel by Adeline Yen Mah.

3.2 Collecting Data

In the process of collecting data, the first step is the researcher reads the whole text of the novel while mark the utterances that indicate the utterance of speech acts. Secondly, the researcher analyze the collected data. Thirdly, the researcher classify into the categories of speech acts in accordance with the formulation problems.

3.3 Data Analysis

The procedures for analyzing data are as follow:(1) analyze the data or utterances which found in the novel, (2) classify the data into the the categories of speech acts, and (3) summarizing the research findings based on the data analysis. In this part, the researcher summarizes the answers to the formulated questions.

IV. FINDING AND DISCUSSION

Table 1

Speech Act	
Locutionary Act	21 utterances
Illocutionary Act	99 utterances
Perlocutionary Act	17 utterances
Total	137utterances

The researcher analyzed the speech acts used in Chinese Cinderella novel based on the utterances that are used in the plot. This study found 137 utterances or conversations are considered as a speech act. For locutionary act used in this novel 21 utterances, an illocutionary act is 99 utterances, and perlocutionary act is 17 utterances.

(1) Locutionary Act

Adeline: "Do you have a picture of my dead mama?"

Aunt Baba: She avoided my eyes. "No. But I have wedding pictures of your father and stepmother Niang. ***Do you want to see them?***"

Adeline: "No. I've seen those before."

The sentence above proves that the utterance or conversation which belongs to locutionary act. A locutionary act is a real message from the speaker to the listener. The utterance "*Do you want to see them*" is the real message that the Aunt Baba as the speaker delivered to the Adeline as the listener.

(2) Illocutionary Act

Adeline : "What did you do that for?" I asked angrily.

Second brother: "Because I feel like it, that's why, you ugly little squirt! ***This'll teach you to show off your medal***"

The sentence above proves that the utterance or conversation which belongs to illocutionary. The utterance "*This'll teach you to show off your medal*" has another meaning, it doesn't mean actually teaching how to show off the medal. The speaker (second brother) was envy to Adeline (listener), so that the utterance represented a jealousy for the award that received by Adeline.

(3) Perlocutionary Act

Go fetch my English-Chinese dictionary. It's on my bed in my room. Niang wants me to translate something."

I was halfway off my chair" when NaiNai said, "Do the translation later! Sit down, Wu Mei."

The sentence above proves that the utterance or conversation which belongs to perlocutionary. Perlocutionary act is when the speaker is saying something, then the listener directly moves and do what the speaker's want. "*I was halfway off my chair*" is the response of the command "*Go fetch my English-Chinese dictionary. It's on my bed in my room*".

Tabel 2

Illocutionary Act	
Assertive	28 utterances
Commissive	16 utterances
Directive	20 utterances
Declarative	13 utterances
Expressive	22 utterances
Total	99 utterances

In this novel, there are a lot of utterances are categorized to the classification of illocutionary acts. There are 99 utterances identified as the illocutionary act. They are: (1) assertive is 28 utterances, (2) commissive is 16 utterances, (3) directive is 20 utterances, (4) declarative is 13 utterances, and (5) expressive is 22 utterances. Therefore, the illocutionary act is the most dominant in this research. Here are the examples and descriptions of the classification of illocutionary acts that are used in the novel:

4.1 Assertive

“For me, no other pet can ever replace PLT . . .” I interrupted rudely because, for a moment, I thought I was going to cry.”

The sentence above proves that the utterance or conversation which belongs to assertive. Assertive act is commit speakers to the truth of some proposition. This utterance purposes to convey the information about the truth statement, that is *“for me, no other pet can ever replace PLT”*.

4.2 Commissive

“Of course I will! We’ll set up house on our own and take PLT with us. We’ll work together in our own bank, side by side.”

The sentence above proves that the utterance or conversation which belongs to commissive. Commissive act is commit speakers to some future action. The utterance *“of course I will! We’ll set up house on our own and take PLT with us. We’ll work together in our own bank, side by side”* represented the intention and promise to some action in the future.

4.3 Directive

“Wu Chun-mei! Stop talking at once and start paying attention!” she commanded in a loud voice. ‘Now I want all of you to listen carefully. Tomorrow is a very special day because it is Election Day.’

The sentence above proves that the utterance or conversation which belongs to directive. Directive act is count as attempt to bring about some effect through the action of hearer e.g. requesting, ordering, demanding, begging, etc. As seen as the example above, the utterance *“Wu Chun-mei! Stop talking at once and start paying attention!”* it indicates as a giving command to the listener, and the listener is following what the speaker said.

4.4 Declarative

“I call it PLT. Precious Little Treasure (Xiao Bao-bei in Chinese) My first pet in my life.”

The sentence above proves that the utterance or conversation which belongs to declarative. Declarative act is speech acts whose successful performance brings about the correspondence between the propositional content and reality. e.g naming a baby/ship, resigning, dismissing, accepting, etc. The utterance *“I call it PLT. Precious Little Treasure”* indicates that the speaker declaring the name of her first pet that is PLT.

4.5 Expressive

“I like you much better when I play only with you,’ I confided one day. ‘You don’t order me around or make me be the bad person all the time when we play “Three Countries War”. *You are fair while the others despise me.”*

The sentence above proves that the utterance or conversation which belongs to expressive. Expressive act is count as the expression of some psychological state. The utterance “*I like you much better when I play only with you. You are fair while the others despise me*” indicates the expression of thanking to someone or something. In this case, the speaker thanked to a bird who had become her only best friend.

V. CONCLUSION

The researcher analyzed the speech acts used in Chinese Cinderella novel based on the utterances that are used in the plot. This study found 137 utterances or conversations are considered as a speech act. For locutionary act used in this novel 21 utterances, an illocutionary act is 99 utterances, and perlocutionary act is 17 utterances. There are 99 utterances identified as the illocutionary act. They are: (1) assertive is 28 utterances, (2) commissive is 16 utterances, (3) directive is 20 utterances, (4) declarative is 13 utterances, and (5) expressive is 22 utterances. The classification of the illocutionary act which is dominant in this novel is assertive with 28 utterances because this novel is an autobiography about an unwanted daughter so that the most of the utterances purpose to convey the information about the truth statement. The result of this research is expected to be references for other students, especially in speech act. In addition, it can be a reference for other researchers who want analyze the same topic with different data and you can explore more sources to develop the research.

VI. Acknowledgements

I would like to express my special thanks of gratitude to my lecturer Dr. Dr. Ichwan Suyudi, MM. who gave me the opportunity to do this research. Secondly, I would also like to thank my family, especially my husband and son, who became my support system in finalizing this research within the limited time frame. Moreover, to all people who helped me to finish this research paper, which I cannot mention them one by one. There are no words that can express my gratitude for what they have done for me. Thank you.

REFERENCES

Journal Papers:

- [1] Tutuarima, Z., Nuraeningsih., Rusiana. 2018. *An Analysis of Speech Act Used in London Has Fallen Movie*. Kudus: Muria Kudus University.

Books:

- [2] Austin, J. L. 1962. *How to do things with words*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press. Cresswell, W., Jhon. 2009. *Research design: qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approach (second edition)*. New Delhi: Sage Publications.
- [3] Mah, A., Y. 2015. *Chinese cinderella*. London: Puffin Books.
- [4] Patton, M., Q. 2002. *Qualitative research and evaluation method*. California: Sage Publications.
- [5] Yule, G. 1996. *Pragmatics*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.